

Agroforestry in Portugal

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- Local, European and CAP policies
- Bureaucracy: management and processing usually at slow pace, administrative forms tedious.
- Fuel Management Policy
- Public policies without adequate strategy
- Legal framework non dynamic. Regulation non adapted to new productive and processing models.

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Spain		Silvopasture	12,22%	15,12%
STATE:	Portugal		Agrisilviculture	0,40%	0,28%
Nut level:	1		Agrosilvopasture	0,18%	0,15%
Eurostat code:	PT1		Kitchen gardens	0,63%	0,91%
Population	2018	2022	Holding type	2016	2023
Population	9.845.729	9.929.630	Natural person (ha)	2.152.930	2.050.200
Density (p km ⁻²)	112	113	Legal person (ha)	1.246.730	1.584.800
Cover data	2018	2022	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	100.850
Forest	41,09%	14,45%	Natural person (holder)	223.500	222.750
Arable land	8,61%	9,79%	Legal person (holder)	11.640	16.650
Permanent crops	1,10%	2,67%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	640
Agroforestry	13,43%	16,45%	Regional Agricultural Area	2016	2023
Shrubland	9,14%	17,97%	Farm number	235.150	240.040
Grassland	14,24%	19,23%	Farm ha (UAA)	3.399.660	3.735.860
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022			

Animal populations (Thousand head)

	2018	2023
Live bovine animals	1.349	1.244
Dairy cows	144	133
Non dairy cows	453	434
Live swine, domestic species	2.168	2.141
Live sheep	2.201	2.205
Live goats	318	324

CROPS (Hectares)

	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	3.399.660	3.735.860
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	251.610	192.080
Common wheat and spelt	34.400	22.380
Durum wheat	5.790	3.980
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	15.960	12.430
Barley	20.770	13.600
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	44.860	25.740
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	76.430	69.370
Rice	29.000	27.210
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	17.400	24.860
Industrial crops	19.740	6.090
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	1.360	730
Fibre crops	-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	1.530	20
Plants harvested green from arable land	416.550	378.690
Green maize	63.640	53.760
Kitchen gardens	15.700	13.900

María Rosa Mosquera Losada, Ana Couso Viana, Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro, Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez & José Javier Santiago Freijanes (2025) Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	7
Forestry	3
Crop diversification including woody perennials	4
Crop rotation including woody perennials	2
Livestock including woody perennials	1
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	0
Interventions	7

References

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- Key farm variables area livestock (LSU) labour force and standard output (SO) by agricultural size of farm (UAA) legal status of holding and NUTS 2 regions (ef_kvareg) https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_KVAAREG
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